

Monarchy and Its Role in Nation Building in Nepal: Unveiling Myths and Historical Realities

Dr. Dhaka Ram Sapkota

Lecturer, Department of History, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences,
Ratna Rajyalaxmi Campus, Tribhuvan University, Kathmandu, Nepal

Dr. Dol Raj Kafle

Associate Professor, Central Department of History, Faculty of Humanities
and Social Sciences, Tribhuvan University, Kathmandu, Nepal

Suggested Citation

Sapkota, D.R., & Kafle, D.R.
(2024). Monarchy and Its Role in
Nation Building in Nepal:
Unveiling Myths and Historical
Realities. *European Journal of
Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(5),
78-85.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(5\).08](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(5).08)

Abstract:

This study critically examines the role of the Shah monarchs in nation-building, exploring the intersection of historical reality and myth. Despite their significant influence, the Shah kings are often viewed through a lens of folklore and myth, which may obscure their actual contributions to national development. Nepal, one of Asia's oldest nations, boasts a rich history spanning over three millennia, during which it has been governed by various dynasties, with the Shah dynasty being the most recent (1768-2006). Situated between China and India, Nepal is known for its diverse historical kings, including the Kiranti, Lichhavi, Malla, and Shah dynasties. This study

investigates how the Shah Dynasty, particularly under Prithvi Narayan Shah, contributed to the formation of modern Nepal and the shaping of national identity. The research addresses two primary questions: Shah Dynasty's impact on nation-building and the contemporary perceptions of their contributions. Utilizing historical methods, this study seeks to clarify the historical accuracy of these myths and their effects on current national identity and development.

Keywords: *Dynasty, History, Monarchy, Nation, Nepal, Politics.*

Introduction

Nepal, one of Asia's oldest nations, has a rich history spanning over three thousand years. Throughout this extensive period, the country has been governed by various dynasties (Shah, 1992). Among these, the Shah dynasty, which ruled from 1768 to 2006, is the most recent. This study examines both the myth and reality of the Shah Monarch's role in nation-building (Shrestha, 2007). While the influence of rulers is crucial in national development, certain folklore and myths have emerged that may distort public perception. Situated in South Asia between

China and India, Nepal is internationally recognized by several descriptors, including the "Land of Peace," the "Land of Mt. Everest," the "Land of Gods and Goddesses," and the "Land of Kings" (Jha, 2014). The country is often associated with a variety of historical kings, including the Kiranti, Lichhavi, Malla, and Shah kings.

In Nepal, various myths and stories have shaped perceptions of kingship and monarchy. Among these, the Shah Dynasty stands out, with numerous myths and historical realities intertwining in popular understanding. This

study delves into these myths and realities related to the Shah Dynasty, aiming to clarify their historical accuracy and impact (Adhikary, 1997). The primary objective is to explore how the Shah Dynasty contributed to nation-building and to examine the relationship between myth and reality in this context (Sharma, 2019). The study focuses on two main research questions: First, did the Shah Dynasty play a significant role in the creative process of nation-building? Second, how do the people of Nepal perceive the Shah Dynasty's contributions to national development? By addressing these questions, the study seeks to provide a nuanced understanding of the Shah Dynasty's historical role and its influence on contemporary perceptions.

Nepal is a nation with a rich monarchical history, situated between China and India. The earliest known king of Nepal was Bhuktaman, the founder of the Gopal Dynasty. Shah (1992) notes that "Nepal was built and unified by the monarchy, regardless of its present context" (p. 341). The historical narrative of Nepal begins with the Kirat Dynasty (800 BC–300 AD), followed by the Lichhavi and Thakuri periods (300–1200 AD), and the Malla period (1200–1769 AD). The establishment of the Shah Dynasty marked a new era in Nepalese history. Prithvi Narayan Shah, who founded the Shah Dynasty, ushered in a transformative period for modern Nepal. This era introduced one of the most dynamic and politically active monarchies, among the few that continue to exist in the world today.

Scholars such as Shah argue that Nepal's existence is deeply intertwined with the efforts of its kings (Paudel, 2017). The history of Nepal includes a succession of notable monarchs from the Gopal Dynasty to the Shah Dynasty. Among these, figures such as Ram Shah, Amshubarma, Jayasthiti Malla, Man Dev, and Prithvi Narayan Shah are recognized for their significant contributions to the country. These kings undertook various benevolent initiatives that shaped Nepal's history. However, some monarchs are also noted for their indulgence in luxury, property accumulation, and personal excesses. Critics like Suryamani Adhikary (1997) emphasize that the Shah kings played a crucial

role in transforming Nepal from a collection of small kingdoms into a unified nation. Their conquests not only expanded the territory but also established sovereignty and fostered a new sense of national identity. The Shah Dynasty, particularly under Prithvi Narayan Shah, was instrumental in laying the foundations for modern Nepal and nurturing the development of nationalism.

During the process of unifying the nation, several mysterious events unfolded under the guise of nationalism and patriotism. Historians and social critics have interpreted these events through their respective lenses. Caplan, for example, views the Shah kings and their troops as invaders who appropriated land and property from various ethnic communities (Tucci, 1977). This perspective is echoed by Aahuti (2012), who similarly portrays the Shah kings as agents of conquest rather than benevolent leaders. Additionally, the residents of Kritipur have also labelled the Shah rulers as criminals, reflecting a broader sentiment of discontent and resistance among some communities.

The role of monarchs in nation-building in Nepal has been the subject of considerable debate. Scholars such as Adhikary (1997), Shah (1992), Vaidya (1985), and Bangdel (2005) highlight the positive contributions of kings and monarchs to the development of the nation. In contrast, critics like Jha (2014), Shrestha (2007), and Anand (2003) challenge this view, arguing that the monarchs' contributions were less favourable. In this context, Michaels, Bajracharya, Niels, and Madeleine (2016) reference Leo Rose, a noted British writer, who criticized the Shah kings. Rose asserted that "the Shah kings, in their pursuit of unifying small kingdoms and consolidating power, undermined national harmony and disregarded the self-governing rights of the people. Prithvi Narayan Shah and his successors conquered autonomous self-governing regions, resulting in widespread violence and the loss of many lives" (p. 34). This view suggests that the Shah kings, particularly, were associated with horror and fear, becoming notorious for their brutal rule.

Shah (1992) offers a critical perspective on the overall history of Nepal, suggesting that Nepali rulers were characterized by corruption and a tendency to dominate the populace. He argues that, given the existence of slavery in Nepal during this period, it is questionable to view the kings as benefactors of the people. The absence of written laws meant that governance was based on the whims of the king and his administrators, casting doubt on the notion that the kings contributed positively to nation-building. Similarly, Jha (2014) contends that the Shah kings not only disrupted national harmony but also exploited the people of the Terai and the high Himalayas. According to Jha, the kings utilized natural resources primarily for their gain, rather than for the benefit of the nation. In alignment with these views, Sharma (2019) argues that the kings lacked a genuine commitment to national development, focusing instead on advancing their own personal or familial interests.

The reviews mentioned above suggest that the role of kings in Nepal was neither entirely formative nor wholly destructive. Despite the land's historical association with monarchy, the shift to a republican system of government in Nepal has prompted renewed scholarly interest in evaluating the kings' contributions to nation-building. Before the establishment of the republic, only a few foreign scholars critiqued the negative impacts of the kings on nation-building. However, in the contemporary context, most scholars have critically examined the role of the kings, highlighting their shortcomings in fostering national development and maintaining peace and harmony in Nepal.

Many writers, researchers, and scholars, both foreign and native, have explored the role of Nepali rulers and monarchs. Despite this extensive body of work, there remains a notable gap in research concerning whether the actions of these monarchs in nation-building were based on myth or reality. To address this gap, this article employs a historical method to critically examine and differentiate the actual impact of the monarchs' rule on the nation's development.

Materials and Methods

This study employed a qualitative research design to investigate the complex and subjective issue of the role of monarchy in Nepal. Given the intricacies involved in analyzing historical and political dynamics, a qualitative approach was deemed most appropriate. Specifically, the interpretive paradigm was utilized to provide a nuanced understanding of the subject matter.

Both primary and secondary data sources were employed in this study. Secondary data were gathered through an extensive review of books, scholarly articles, and previously published reports. This information was obtained through library research, which provided a foundation for understanding existing literature and historical context.

Primary data were collected via field study to gain firsthand insights into the contemporary perspectives on the role of monarchy. Purposive random sampling was used to select a representative sample of individuals actively engaged in teaching and writing about history. The sample comprised five participants: two politicians, two historians, and one independent journalist.

In-depth interviews served as the primary data collection method. The interviews aimed to capture detailed and varied viewpoints on the role of the monarchy in nation-building. Each participant was assigned an identifier: P1 for Participant One, P2 for Participant Two, P3 for Participant Three, P4 for Participant Four, and P5 for Participant Five.

Discussion

The role of kings and the monarchical system of government in Nepal has had both positive and negative impacts on nation-building, as perceived differently by scholars. Participant P1 observed, "When discussing the role of kings in nation-building, particularly referring to the Shah Dynasty, it is believed that Prithvi Narayan Shah had a significant impact through his military conquests (Hasrat, 1970). However, it is unclear whether he contributed to economic

development. Some scholars reference the 'Dibya Updesh' (Pradhan, K. (1991) as a source of valuable suggestions for peace, harmony, and economic progress, but these recommendations were never implemented in Nepal."

P1 further noted, "Following Prithvi Narayan Shah, King Tribhuvan played a pivotal role in establishing democracy in Nepal. In my view, apart from these two kings, the other monarchs did not contribute effectively to nation-building. King Mahendra, for instance, promoted a sense of unity under the banner of nationalism but simultaneously repressed marginalized cultural communities. The last king, Gyanendra, also failed to foster peace, harmony, and development in the nation." This perspective highlights the complex legacy of the monarchy in Nepal and its varied contributions to the country's development.

The role of the Shah kings in nation-building is a topic of significant debate. While much attention has been given to the contributions of Prithvi Narayan Shah, there is considerable ambiguity regarding the developmental impact of other kings and queens. Participant P1 specifically noted the substantial role of Prithvi Narayan Shah in unifying Nepal but expressed uncertainty about the development efforts of his successors. P1 also highlighted the contributions of King Tribhuvan, who struggled against the Rana regime to re-establish a functioning monarchy in Nepal. Despite his efforts to introduce democratic reforms, Tribhuvan's reign was relatively short-lived, as he passed away in 1954. After his death, King Mahendra ascended the throne and brought forth a distinct vision for national development.

Mahendra introduced a unique concept of democracy known as *Matosubaundo prajatantra* (democracy suitable to the soil). This form of democracy emphasized development and decentralization, diverging from multi-party democracy which he believed would not foster lasting peace, stability, or prosperity. During Mahendra's rule, significant infrastructure projects were undertaken, including major highways, hydroelectric power projects, and administrative buildings. Despite these

achievements, his reign was criticized by foreign observers and political leaders, who often labelled him as a cruel tyrant. This characterization is considered by some as unjust, given his contributions to national development.

Following Mahendra's death in 1971, his son, King Birendra, succeeded him and continued his father's development initiatives. Birendra launched long-term development plans aimed at furthering nation-building. However, his efforts were frequently undermined by political parties and foreign entities who were wary of the monarch's influential role in Nepal's political landscape (Upreti & Pyakurel, 2012). As a result, Birendra's role was increasingly constrained to that of a constitutional monarch, with persistent obstacles impeding his development agenda. This analysis underscores the complex and often contested legacy of the Shah kings in Nepal's historical and developmental narrative.

The abolition of the monarchy and the establishment of a republican government in Nepal were intended to bring about peace, prosperity, and happiness. However, these promises have not been fully realized, leading to increasing scepticism among the populace regarding both democratic and monarchical systems (Upreti, 2006). In line with the views of Participant P1 and has also criticized the effectiveness of democracy in Nepal. Upreti argues that while democracy is a constitutional right, it has proven to be a failed project in the Nepali context (2014). According to Upreti, political leaders in Nepal have not adhered to democratic principles and the norms of a republic, undermining the effective implementation of democratic values.

In this context, Participant P3 observed, "Nation-building in Nepal remains an unfinished project because there has been a lack of effective efforts and clear parameters for its advancement. The process has become a political issue, as political parties focus on promoting democracy while the monarchy emphasized infrastructure development. The roles of historical figures like Prithvi Narayan Shah, Tribhuvan, and Mahendra remain controversial and divisive among the public.

These kings are often seen as prioritizing personal interests and using national resources for their family's benefit, which has led to controversy surrounding their contributions to nation-building.”

Nation-building is a critical objective for Nepal, and each political party claims that it can achieve this goal under its leadership. Fisher (2001) argues that the challenge of nation-building is not unique to Nepal or Asia, as many Asian countries faced similar struggles after decolonization. Nations like Indonesia, Malaysia, and India successfully implemented clear nation-building strategies, with political leaders working towards this goal (Malla, 1983). In contrast, Nepal's nation-building efforts have remained incomplete, with both political leaders and kings seeking personal acclaim rather than focusing on a coherent and unified approach.

Without a well-defined roadmap and a sense of collective purpose, the nation-building project in Nepal continues to be a subject of ongoing discussion and debate (Lawoti & Susan 2013). The lack of a unified vision and effective execution has left the project unresolved, highlighting the need for a more strategic and collaborative effort in the future.

The Constitution of Nepal 2015 addressed the long-standing aspirations for nation-building by introducing a new definition of the nation that acknowledges Nepal's rich diversity. According to Article 3 of the Constitution, the nation is defined as: "All the Nepalese people, with multiethnic, multilingual, multi-religious, multicultural characteristics and in geographical diversities, and having common aspirations and being united by a bond of allegiance to national independence, territorial integrity, national interest and prosperity of Nepal, collectively constitute the nation" (p. 31). This article represents a significant shift, as it explicitly recognizes and values the country's diverse ethnic, linguistic, religious, and cultural identities, aiming to foster unity amidst diversity.

In contrast, the earlier Constitution of Nepal in 1962 presented a different perspective on nationhood. Article 2 of this constitution described the nation as: "The Nation (i) Having

common aspirations and united by the common bond of allegiance to the Crown, the Nepalese people irrespective of religion, race, caste or tribe collectively constitute the nation; (ii) It is the indefeasible and inalienable right of the nation to develop its political, economic, and cultural life and to determine its relations with other nations, following its genius and traditions." This earlier definition emphasized unity under the monarchy and focused on the nation's right to self-determination and development.

The transition from the 1962 Constitution to the 2015 Constitution reflects a broader understanding of nationhood, aiming to embrace Nepal's multi-faceted identity while striving to unite its diverse population under a common national framework. This evolution underscores the ongoing effort to reconcile the nation's historical complexities with contemporary aspirations for inclusivity and unity.

The Constitution of Nepal 2015 emphasizes diversity management as a core aspect of nation-building. This approach marks a significant departure from the previous constitutions. The Constitution of Nepal 1962 primarily focused on economic prosperity and socio-cultural enhancement, while the Constitution of Nepal 1990, known for its democratic reforms, highlighted the importance of communal unity and shared identity as central to nation-building. According to Article 2 of the 1990 Constitution: "The Nation, having common aspirations and united by a bond of allegiance to national independence and integrity of Nepal, comprises the Nepalese people irrespective of religion, race, caste, or tribe" (p.31). This provision underscored the significance of unity amidst diversity.

Historically, the concept of nationality in Nepal has evolved, reflecting shifting priorities and perspectives on nation-building. The changing definitions and emphases over time have contributed to a complex and sometimes contradictory view of what constitutes nationhood (Thapa, & Sijapati 2004). This evolving understanding has led to confusion regarding the nation-building project in Nepal,

as different groups advocate for either unity or diversity.

Participant P4 commented on this issue, stating, "Unity and diversity are fundamental features of Nepal. However, there are divergent views on these concepts. Some advocate for emphasizing diversity, while others stress the importance of unity (Foucault, 2000). The nation-building project in Nepal encompasses both unity and diversity. Political parties have focused on managing diversity through the implementation of a federal system, while royalists and so-called nationalists have called for a renewed focus on national unity" (Government of Nepal, 990).

This dichotomy between unity and diversity reflects the ongoing challenges in Nepal's nation-building efforts. The tension between these two goals highlights the difficulty in crafting a cohesive national identity while accommodating the country's rich ethnic and cultural diversity (Tamang, 2006). As Nepal continues to navigate these complex issues, the quest for a balanced and inclusive approach to nation-building remains a central concern.

The ongoing debate about nation-building in Nepal highlights the persistent struggles with poverty and unemployment. Throughout its modern history, Nepal has drafted seven constitutions, with five of these constitutions failing to achieve long-term stability (Acharya, 2017). The current, sixth constitution, which introduces a new concept of nation-building that addresses the country's diverse ethnic and cultural landscape, is still in the process of implementation.

One of the major challenges in Nepal's nation-building efforts is the lack of deepened democracy, particularly at the grassroots level. As noted by Giri (2018), without a robust democratic foundation that extends to local communities, effective nation-building remains elusive. The restructuring of Nepal continues to be a contentious issue, with ongoing doubts about the sustainability of democracy (Dahal, 2001). Human rights conditions are troubling, and indicators of good governance are marred by violence, corruption, and systemic injustices.

The concept of nation-building has largely remained a political slogan rather than a practical reality. The gap between political promises and functional implementation persists, leaving Nepal in a state of transition both politically and administratively. The agenda for nation-building has not yet been fully realized, and the country continues to grapple with the challenge of translating its constitutional aspirations into effective governance and socio-economic development (Government of Nepal, 1962). While the constitution of Nepal 2015 introduced significant reforms aimed at addressing diversity and improving nation-building efforts, the practical application of these reforms has been hindered by deep-rooted issues in democracy and governance (Government of Nepal (2015). The transition remains incomplete, and the nation faces ongoing challenges in achieving its developmental and democratic goals.

Conclusion

The historical legacy of Nepal's monarchy has been characterized by the creation of a mythic narrative wherein the kings were portrayed as divine incarnations, or 'Dev' Gods, wielding absolute power over their subjects. This narrative was used to legitimize their authority and justify the accumulation of material wealth and territorial expansion. However, the focus of the monarchy often failed to prioritize the welfare and development of the people. Consequently, many Nepalis have perceived the kings' role in nation-building as largely illusory, viewing their contributions as more symbolic than substantive. Following the abolition of the monarchy and the establishment of a republic, the mythological narratives surrounding the kings have been officially discarded. Nonetheless, the new republican political structure has, in many ways, mirrored the failings of the previous regimes. The persistent issues of governance, political dysfunction, and inadequate development have continued to undermine the goals of nation-building.

To prevent democracy from becoming a transient phase rather than a sustainable system, political parties, civil society, and government

institutions in Nepal must work collaboratively to address these systemic problems. A concerted effort is needed to rectify past mistakes, implement effective governance strategies, and focus on genuine development. Only through such cooperative and committed action can the nation move beyond the myths of its past and transform the vision of a unified and prosperous Nepal into a tangible reality. In conclusion, while the transition from monarchy to republic has marked a significant shift in Nepal's political landscape, the challenges of nation-building remain unresolved. The lessons from historical failures must guide contemporary efforts to ensure that democratic ideals are not only embraced but effectively realized. The collective responsibility of all stakeholders is crucial to achieving lasting progress and fulfilling the true promise of nation-building in Nepal.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Aahuti, (2012). Ekikaran maa samrajyabad [Imperialism in unification]. *Chitwan Post*. 20(14), 2.
- Acharya, N. (2017). *Journey to the Republic*. Sagrila Books.
- Adhikary, S. M. (1997). *The Khasa Kingdom: A Trans-Himalayan Empire of the Middle Age*.
- Anand, J. (2003). *Prison of authority, my memory*. Madheshi Human Rights Protection Center.
- Bangdel, L. S. (2005). *The statue of Jay Varma and varmadynasty in Nepal*. Mandala Books.
- Constituent Assembly Darpan (ed.) (2008-2011). *Legislature-Parliament Secretariat*. Constituent Assembly Darpan
- Dahal, R. K. (2001). *Constitutional and political development in Nepal*. Ratana Pustak Bhandar.
- Fisher, W. F. (2001). *Fluid boundaries forming and transforming identity in Nepal*. Columbia University Press.
- Foucault, M. (2000). For an ethics of discomfort. In J. D. Faubion (Ed.). *Power: Essential Works of Foucault, 1954-1984* (Volume III, pp. 443-448). The New Press.
- Giri, K. (2018). Book Review: Kalpan Jha. 2017. The Madhesi Upsurge and the Contested Idea of Nepal. *Journal of Asian Security and International Affairs*, 5(1), 105-107. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2347797017751713>
- Government of Nepal (1962). *Constitution of Nepal 1962*. Pairabi Book House.
- Government of Nepal (1990). *Constitution of Nepal 1990*. Pairabi Book House.
- Government of Nepal (2015). *Constitution of Nepal 2015*. Pairabi Book House.
- Hasrat, B. J. (1970). *History of Nepal: As told by its own and contemporary chroniclers*. Hoshiarpur.
- Jha, P. (2014). *Battles of the New Republic: A contemporary history of Nepal*. Oxford University Press.
- Lawoti, M. & Susan, H, (eds.) (2013), *Nationalism and ethnic conflict in Nepal: Identities and mobilization after 1990*. Routledge.
- Malla, K. (1983). Nepal archaeological of the world. 3rd PATA International Tourism & Heritage Conservation Conference (1-4 November). *The Nepal Heritage Society Souvenir for the PATA conference*. Kathmandu, pp. 33-39 on 22 March 2012.
- Michaels, A., Bajracharya, M., Niels, G. & Madeleine, H. (2016). Nepalese history in a European experience: A case study intracultural historiography. *History and theory*, 55(2), 210-232.
- Nirala Publications.
- Paudel, K. (2017) History of Shah Dynasty in Nepal. *Research Orchard*. 15(30), 26-37.
- Pradhan, K. (1991). *The Gorkha conquests: The process and consequences of the unification of Nepal, with particular reference to eastern Nepal*. Oxford University Press.
- Shah, R. (1992). *Ancient and medieval Nepal*. Manohar Publications.

Sharma, S. (2019). *The Nepal nexus: An inside account of the Maoists, the Durbar and New Delhi*. Penguin Random House India Private Limited.

Shrestha, B. G. (August 12, 2007). The death of divine kingship in Nepal: Nepal's move from autocratic monarchy to a fragile republican state. *Spotlight*, pp. 195-207.

Tamang, S. (2006). *Restructuring of state in Nepal's context*. Samana Praksan.

Thapa, D. & Sijapati, B. (2004). *A kingdom under siege: Nepal's Maoist insurgency, 1996 to 2004*. Bloomsbury Academic.

Tucci, G. (1977). *Journey to Mustang, 1952*. (2nd ed.). Diana Fussell.

Upreti, B. C. & Pyakurel, U. P. (ed.) (2012). *Contemporary Nepal*. Kalinga Publication.

Upreti, B. C. (2006). Nationalism in South Asia: Trends and interpretations. *Indian political science association*, 67(3), 535-544.

Upreti, B. R. (2014). *Nationalism and militarization in Nepal*. Nepal Centre.

Vaidya, T. R. (1985). *Crime and punishment in Nepal: A historical perspective*. Bini Vaidya And Purna Devi Manandhar.